

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

An updated checklist of encyrtid wasps (Hymenoptera, Encyrtidae) from Iraq

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Abstract

This study presented the first an updated list of encyrtid species (Hymenoptera, Encyrtidae), which found in Iraq. The list contains the following two subfamilies, with genera and species count: Encyrtinae (seven species, six genera), and Tetracneminae (10 species, four genera). The synonyms and global distribution of the species were given based on the previous literature. The current list provides important information for researchers interested in the field of biological control.

Keywords: Biological Control; Chalcidoidea; Encyrtid Wasps; Hymenoptera; Parasitoids; Phenacoccus

1. Introduction

With over 4170 known species, the huge family Encyrtidae is a part of the Chalcidoidea superfamily and is found all over the world (1). It is among the most significant biological control of plant-harming insect species; they are effectively utilized in tandem with Aphelinidae to combat several pest species, especially scale insects (2). In addition to Noyes and Hayat (3), they confirmed that this family's members are an important wasp family since they reduce the numbers of numerous pests that affect cultivated plants in fields and forests. According to Guerrieri and Noyes (4), these wasps are well-known parasitizes (as primary end parasitoids or hyper parasitoids, whatever the case may be), a diverse range of host insects that include members of Diptera, Coleoptera, Hemiptera, Lepidoptera, Hymenoptera, Orthoptera, and Neuroptera, as well as Arachnida, primarily spiders and ticks. As a result, more than 400 species have been employed as biological control agents for numerous insect pests in studies conducted worldwide (5).

This family has little researches in Iraq; however, a few publications featuring generic checklists have been written about it; there were different references about this matter: (3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, and 11), all of whom identified one species. Four species were listed by in (12), however. *Aenasius arizonensis* (Girault, 1915) was recently identified by Abdul-Rassoul (13) from Iraq as a parasitoid on *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsly, 1898, Noyes (5) compiled a list of 62 species for Iraq.

Based on recent literature, the goal of this study is to present a review with an updated list of Encyrtidae species, along with revealing to synonyms, basionyms, and global distribution.

2. Materials and Methods

This checklist, which is based on GBIF Secretariat (1), Noyes and Hayat (3), and Noyes (5, 14), includes the nomenclature, higher classification, basionyms, synonyms, and global distribution. Ordered alphabetically are the genera, species, and subfamilies. The list was presented based on the references available at the update of writing this article and referred to in the results.

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3. Results and Discussion

The species of encrypted wasps that distributed in Iraq are listed below:

3.1. Subfamily: Encyrtinae Madl, 2023

3.1.1. Genus, *Aenasius* Walker, 1846

Synonyms: *Neodiscodes* Compere, 1931
Chalcaspis Howard, 1895

Aenasius arizonensis (Girault, 1915)

Synonym: *Chalcaspis arizonensis* Girault, 1915

Distribution: Iraq (13). China, Pakistan, India, USA (14), and Iran (15).

Host: According to Noyes (14) this parasitoid is common on *Pseudococcus longispinus* (Targioni Tozzetti, 1867), and *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley, 1898.

3.1.2. Genus, *Blastothrix* Mayr, 1876

Blastothrix sp.

Distribution: This genus is widely distributed throughout the Palearctic Region (16). This genus was reported in Iraq without identified species Iraq (17).

Host: *Eulecanium tiliae* (L., 1758) (Hemiptera, Coccidae) (18).

3.1.3. Genus, *Cheiloneurus* Westwood, 1833

Synonyms: *Bekilyia* Risbec, 1952
Chiloneurus Förster, 1856
Chrysopophagoides Girault, 1915
Chrysopophagus Ashmead, 1894
Epicheiloneurus Girault, 1915
Eusemionella Girault, 1915
Lepidoneurus Hoffer, 1957
Metacheiloneurus Hoffer, 1957
Procheiloneurus Girault, 1920
Saronotum Perkins, 1906
Cheiloneurus sp.

Distribution: This genus is widely distributed throughout the Palearctic Region. This genus was recoded in Iraq without determined the species (17).

Host: *Eulecanium tiliae* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Hemiptera, Coccidae) (18).

3.1.4. Genus, *Encyrtus* Latreille, 1809

Synonyms: *Allorhypoideus* Brethes, 1916
Eucomys Forster, 1856
Howardia Dalla Torre, 1897
Prorhypoideus Brethes, 1921

***Encyrtus* sp.**

Distribution: This genus is widely distributed throughout the Palearctic region (16). It was reported in Iraq without identified species (17).

Host: *Eulecanium tiliae* (18).

3.1.5. Genus, *Eusemion* Dahlbom, 1857

***Eusemion* sp.**

Distribution: This genus is widely distributed throughout the Palearctic region. In his survey, (17) noted this genus for Iraq under the unidentified species.

Host: *Eulecanium tiliae* (18).

3.1.6. Genus, *Prochiloneurus* Silvestri, 1915

Synonyms: *Achrysopophagus* Girault, 1915
Parachrysopophagus Agarwal, 1965

Prochiloneurus aegyptiacus (Mercet, 1929)

Basionym: *Achrysopophagus aegyptiacus* Mercet, 1929

Distribution: Afrotropical: Eritrea, Gabon, Ghana, Namibia, Nigeria, Congo, South Africa, Tanzania, and Togo; Oriental and Palaearctic regions (19). India (20).

Host: *Pseudococcus* sp. (Hemiptera, Pseudococcidae) (21).

Prochiloneurus io (Girault, 1920)

Synonym: *Achrysopophagus io* Girault, 1920

Distribution: Iraq (12); Puerto Rico, China, and Philippines (3, 22).

Host: According to (3), there were many hosts belonging to the Pseudococcidae for this species, including *Heliococcus* sp., *Nipaecoccus vastator*, *N. viridis*, *Planococcus citri*, and *Pseudococcus citri*.

3.2. Subfamily: Tetracneminae Howard, 1892

3.2.1. Genus, *Anagyrus* Howard, 1896

Synonyms: *Anathrix* Burks, 1952
Doliphoceras Mercet, 1921
Gyranusa Mercet, 1921
Heterarthrellus Howard, 1898
Paranusia Brethes, 1913
Protanagyrus Blanchard, 1940
Xiphomastix De Santis, 1972

Host: The species of *Anagyrus* are parasitoids on Mealybug (Pseudococcidae) (23).

Anagyrus abdurrassouli Myartseva, Sugonjaev & Trjapitzin, 1982

Distribution: This species is distributed in Iraq only (12).

Anagyrus aligarhensis Agarwal & Alam, 1959

Synonyms: *Anagyrus diversicornis* Mercet, 1921
Anagyrus opacus (Mercet, 1921)
Anagyrus punctulatus Agarwal & Alam, 1959

Distribution: Bulgaria, France, Turkey, England, Spain, Russia, Portugal, Italy, Hungary, former Yugoslavia, Romania, China, Iran, India, Nepal, and Indonesia (3, 25, 26).

Host: *Pseudococcus viburni* (3, 25, 27).

Anagyrus bohemani (Westwood, 1837)

Basionym: *Encyrtus bohemanni* Westwood, 1837

Synonyms: *Anagyrus mayri* Ruschka, 1923
Anagyrus quercicola Mercet, 1921
Anagyrus singularis Hoffer, 1953
Blastothrix mayri Ruschka, 1923

Distribution: Austria, Canary Islands, France, Spain, Czech Republic, Netherlands, Slovakia, Hungary, Madeira, Portugal, Morocco, Azerbaijan, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine, UK, Poland, and Russia (1).

Anagyrus dactylopii (Howard, 1898)

Basionym: *Aphycus dactylopii* Howard, 1898

Synonyms: *Anagyrus citri* Agarwal, 1965
Anagyrus scutomaculatus Agarwal, 1965

Distribution: Oriental, South Africa, and Palaearctic regions, and India (28).

Host: *Nipaecoccus viridis* (29).

Anagyrus diversicornis (Howard, 1894)

Basionym: *Copidosoma diversicornis* Howard, 1894

Synonyms: *Apoanagyrus diversicornis* (Howard, 1894)

Litomastix diversicornis (Howard, 1894)

Distribution: This species is nearly worldwide (1).

Host: *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (25).

Anagyrus pseudococci (Girault, 1915)

Basionym: *Epidinocarsis pseudococci* Girault, 1915

Synonyms: *Anagirus pseudococci* (Girault, 1915)

Epidinocarsis pseudococci Girault, 1915

Distribution: China, Cyprus, Egypt, Italy, Mediterranean region of Europe (Catania, Sicily) California, Brazilian, Argentina (30, 24, 3). Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, former USSR. South Africa and USA (31). South America (32).

3.2.2. Genus, *Psyllaephagus* Ashmead, 1900

Synonyms: *Anagyropsis* Girault, 1917

Anisodromus Riek, 1962

Calluniphilus Erdos, 1961

Calocerineloides Girault, 1913

Epanagyrus Girault, 1915

Kaszabicyrtus Szelenyi, 1971

Mercetia Bakkendorf, 1965

Metaprionomitus Mercet, 1921

Mirocerus Ashmead, 1904

Neanagyrus Girault, 1915

Ooencyrtoides Hoffer, 1963

Propsyllaephagus Blanchard, 1964

Psyllencyrtus Tachikawa, 1955

Shakespeareia Girault, 1928

Psyllaephagus cellulatus Waterston, 1922

Distribution: Iraq, Croatia, Ghana, Iran and Montenegro (33, 34, 35, 36, 37).

Host: Psyllid species (Hemiptera) (38).

3.3. Genus, *Syrphophagus* Ashmead, 1900

Synonyms: *Aphidencyrtus* Ashmead, 1900

Hexanusia Girault, 1922

Syrphidencyrtus Blanchard, 1940

Syrphophagus aphidivorus (Mayr, 1876)

Basionym: *Encyrtus aphidivorus* Mayr, 1876

Synonyms: *Syrphophagus aphidivorus* (Mayr, 1876)

Aphidencyrtus aphidivorus (Mayr, 1876)

Aphidencyrtus megourae (Ashmead, 1887)

Aphidencyrtus websteri (Howard, 1890)

Syrphophagus aphidiphagus Ashmead, 1887

S. megourae Ashmead, 1887

S. psyllae Kaul & Agarwal, 1986

S. schizoneurae Ashmead, 1885

S. silvestrinus Ghesquière, 1956

S. websteri Howard, 1890

Distribution: Holarctic Region; India, and recently recorded in KSA (38).

Hosts: Agromyzidae, Aleyrodidae, and Aphididae (14).

Syrphophagus nigrocyaneus Ashmead, 1904

Distribution: Iraq (11); South Africa, Palaearctic Region, Afrotropical, China, and Japan (16).

Host: *Syrphus* species pupae (26).

3.3.1. Genus, *Apoleptomastix* Kerrich, 1982

Apoleptomastix bicoloricornis (Girault, 1915)

Basionym: *Leptomastix bicoloricornis* Girault, 1915

Synonyms: *Apoleptomastix spoliata* Kerrich, 1982

Xiphomastix ranchiensis Shamim and Shafee, 1984

Distribution: Iraq (39). Australian and Oriental Regions (3, 40); Tajikistan, Egypt and Saudi Arabia (41).

Host: *Coccidohystrix insolita* (Green, 1908) (42); *Brevennia rehi* (43).

4. Conclusion

By reviewing the references, we can see the importance of studying this group of encyrtid wasps for the purpose of benefiting from them in biological control, especially since the diversity of these wasps somewhat a good in the Iraqi environment.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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